

> restart;

> # Let Phi[XY] be analogous of F[XY] but without replacement. Then

> eqn1 := F[ff] = $\frac{1}{2 \cdot N} + \frac{(N-1)}{N} \cdot \left(s^2 \cdot \text{Phi}[ff] + 2 \cdot s \cdot (1-s) \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2} \cdot F[ff] + \frac{1}{2} \cdot F[fm] \right) + (1-s)^2 \cdot Fbar \right);$

$$eqn1 := F_{ff} = \frac{1}{2N} + \frac{(N-1) \left(s^2 \Phi_{ff} + 2s(1-s) \left(\frac{F_{ff}}{2} + \frac{F_{fm}}{2} \right) + (1-s)^2 Fbar \right)}{N} \quad (1)$$

> eqn2 := F[fm] = $\frac{(N-1)}{N} \cdot \left(s^2 \cdot \text{Phi}[fm] + s \cdot (1-s) \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2} \cdot F[mm] + \frac{1}{2} \cdot F[fm] \right) \right);$

$$eqn2 := F_{fm} = \frac{(N-1) \left(s^2 \Phi_{fm} + s(1-s) \left(\frac{F_{mm}}{2} + \frac{F_{fm}}{2} \right) \right)}{N} \quad (2)$$

> eqn3 := F[mm] = $\frac{1}{2 \cdot N};$

$$eqn3 := F_{mm} = \frac{1}{2N} \quad (3)$$

> eqn4 := Fbar = $\frac{F[ff]}{4} + \frac{F[fm]}{2} + \frac{F[mm]}{4};$

$$eqn4 := Fbar = \frac{F_{ff}}{4} + \frac{F_{fm}}{2} + \frac{F_{mm}}{4} \quad (4)$$

> eqn5 := F[ff] = $\frac{1}{2 \cdot N} + \frac{(N-1)}{N} \cdot \text{Phi}[ff];$

$$eqn5 := F_{ff} = \frac{1}{2N} + \frac{(N-1) \Phi_{ff}}{N} \quad (5)$$

> eqn6 := F[fm] = $\frac{(N-1)}{N} \cdot \text{Phi}[fm];$

$$eqn6 := F_{fm} = \frac{(N-1) \Phi_{fm}}{N} \quad (6)$$

>

> soln := solve({eqn1, eqn2, eqn3, eqn4, eqn5, eqn6}, {F[ff], F[fm], F[mm], Fbar, Phi[ff], Phi[fm]});

$$soln := \left\{ Fbar = \frac{s+1}{sN+3N+3s+1}, F_{ff} = \frac{5N^2s^2+13N^2s+10N^2+2sN+3s^2-2N+s}{2(sN+2N+s)(sN+3N+3s+1)N}, F_{fm} = \frac{(N-1)s}{2N(sN+2N+s)}, F_{mm} = \frac{1}{2N}, \Phi_{ff} = \frac{2(s^2+2s+1)N}{(sN+2N+s)(sN+3N+3s+1)}, \Phi_{fm} = \frac{s}{2(sN+2N+s)} \right\} \quad (7)$$

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> Fff := simplify(rhs(soln[2]), size); Ffm := rhs(soln[3]); Fmm := rhs(soln[4]);
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$$Fff := \frac{(5s^2 + 13s + 10)N^2 + (2s - 2)N + 3s^2 + s}{2N((s + 3)N + 3s + 1)((s + 2)N + s)}$$

$$Ffm := \frac{(N - 1)s}{2N(sN + 2N + s)}$$

$$Fmm := \frac{1}{2N} \quad (8)$$

```
> rbarff := Fff + Ffm;
```

$$rbarff := \frac{(5s^2 + 13s + 10)N^2 + (2s - 2)N + 3s^2 + s}{2N((s + 3)N + 3s + 1)((s + 2)N + s)} + \frac{(N - 1)s}{2N(sN + 2N + s)} \quad (9)$$

```
> rbarfm := Ffm + Fmm
```

$$rbarfm := \frac{(N - 1)s}{2N(sN + 2N + s)} + \frac{1}{2N} \quad (10)$$

```
> # solve eq 14 in Wild 2006 assuming maternal control
```

```
> eqn14_mat_ctrl := (1 - z) / z = (1/2 - rbarff) / (1/2)
```

$$eqn14_mat_ctrl := \frac{1 - z}{z} = 1 - \frac{(5s^2 + 13s + 10)N^2 + (2s - 2)N + 3s^2 + s}{N((s + 3)N + 3s + 1)((s + 2)N + s)} - \frac{(N - 1)s}{N(sN + 2N + s)} \quad (11)$$

```
> zstar_mat_ctrl := simplify(solve(eqn14_mat_ctrl, z), size);
```

$$zstar_mat_ctrl := \frac{((s + 3)N + 3s + 1)((s + 2)N + s)}{(2s^2 + 10s + 12)N^2 + (2s^2 + 4s - 6)N + 4s^2 + 2s + 2} \quad (12)$$

```
> # solve eq 14 in Wild 2006 assuming paternal control
```

```
> eqn14_pat_ctrl := (1 - z) / z = (1/2 - rbarfm) / (1/2)
```

$$eqn14_pat_ctrl := \frac{1 - z}{z} = 1 - \frac{(N - 1)s}{N(sN + 2N + s)} - \frac{1}{N} \quad (13)$$

```
> zstar_pat_ctrl := simplify(solve(eqn14_pat_ctrl, z), size);
```

$$zstar_pat_ctrl := \frac{(s + 2)N + s}{-2 + (2s + 4)N} \quad (14)$$

```
> solve(eqn14_pat_ctrl, z) : Fig2_pat := factor(%);
```

$$Fig2_pat := \frac{sN + 2N + s}{2(sN + 2N - 1)} \quad (15)$$

```

> # Figure 1 panels
> with(plots) :
> P[1] := plot(subs(N=2, zstar_mat_ctrl), s=0..1, color='RED') :
> P[2] := plot(subs(N=2, zstar_pat_ctrl), s=0..1, color='BLUE') :
> P[3] := plot(subs([N=2, s=0], zstar_mat_ctrl), s=0..1, linestyle=DASH, color='RED') :
> P[4] := plot(subs([N=2, s=0], zstar_pat_ctrl), s=0..1, linestyle=DASH, color='BLUE') :
> display(seq(P[k], k=1..4), labels=[`adult survival, s`, `prop invest in sons, z*`], labeldirections
= [HORIZONTAL, VERTICAL], view=[0..1, 0.5..1], labelfont=[HELVETICA, 18]);

```



```

>
> P[5] := plot(subs(N=2, zstar_mat_ctrl - zstar_pat_ctrl), s=0..1, color='CYAN') :
> P[6] := plot(subs(N=5, zstar_mat_ctrl - zstar_pat_ctrl), s=0..1, color='MAGENTA') :
> P[7] := plot(subs(N=10, zstar_mat_ctrl - zstar_pat_ctrl), s=0..1, color='BLACK') :
> display(seq(P[k], k=5..7), labels=[`adult survival, s`, `extent of conflict, mat z· -pat z·`],
labeldirections=[HORIZONTAL, VERTICAL], view=[0..1, 0..0.12], labelfont
= [HELVETICA, 18]);

```

